

Transcriptional regulator LIM-domain-only 4 (LMO4) protein: The role in human immune system

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An organism responds to a diversity of cellular signals by various molecular mechanisms. Transcriptional regulation is one such biological process. Transcriptional regulation coordinates cellular activity and cell identity during development. LIM-domain transcriptional regulator proteins are the family of proteins that are essential in a wide variety of cellular processes. All members of the human LIM-domain-only (LMO) proteins orchestrate many developmental processes and they are intimated at the beginning of the progression of several cancers, including T cell leukemia, breast cancer, gastric cancer, neuroblastoma, etc., as a transcription regulator. Because of the building protein-protein interaction ability of the LIM domain, LMO4 protein shows a function for the formation of new transcriptional complexes and is able to regulate gene expression programs. Furthermore, LMO4 is considered a crucial part of the regulation of immune system programming and nervous system cells. Current research works highlight the therapeutic role of targeting LMO4 in cancer, neurodegenerative disease, and immune system disorders. In this review, we summarized research focused on the role of LMO4 protein in immune system cells. Immune cells are essential in all biological processes; they are important for initiating and terminating cancer and tumor immune escape. Since the LMO4 protein acts in the spatial and temporal manner to activate and repress cellular processes, we conclude that to regulate these processes is needed to obtain gain-of-function and loss-of-function mutants of LMO4 dependent on the cells they are used. Generally, by understanding the role of LMO4 in the human immune system, we will be able to gain insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying immune responses and immune-related diseases.

Keywords: Adaptive immunity, immune cells, innate immunity, human, LIM-domain proteins, LMO4, transcriptional regulation

INTRODUCTION

Transcriptional regulation (TR) is a biological process that lets the cell or an organism respond to a diversity of cellular signals. TR defines cell identity during development and coordinates cellular activity. This dynamic mechanism consists of a series of biological events orchestrated by a massive number of molecules forming greater networks. TR takes place through various temporal and functional steps such as the formation of specific DNA-protein interactions and the assembly of nucleoprotein complexes. A number of molecules and molecular factors are known to participate in TR (Lee et al., 2013).

LIM-domain-only (LMO) proteins are such TR molecules. Termed by the initials of the three homeodomain proteins Lin11, Isl-1 and Mec-3, the LIM domain has proved to be a conserved domain containing *zinc-finger* found in proteins from a

variety of organisms (Bach et al., 2000). The LMO family are transcriptional regulatory proteins that act as molecular adapters as scaffolds for DNA-binding complexes and have important roles in cell fate, tissue modeling, and organ development. LMO4 was first identified as an auto-oncogene in breast cancer (Kwong et al., 2011; Racevskis et al., 1999; Sum et al; 2005). It is known that this gene causes cancer by inhibiting the tumor suppressor gene- BRCA1 (Breast Cancer gene 1) gene in breast epithelial cells. Although high levels are restricted in specific cell types, the LMO4 gene is expressed in embryonic and adult tissues (Sum et al., 2002).

LMO4 is located on chromosome 1p22.3 in the human genome and consists of 165 amino acids. With short aminoterminal (22 residues) and carboxyl-terminal stretches (25 residues), LMO4 has two tandem non-DNA binding LIM domains that are separated by two amino acids. LIM domain

is a special double-zinc finger motif found in a variety of proteins including homeodomain transcription factors, kinases, and adaptors. LMO proteins seem to function as docking sites for other protein factors, leading to the assembly of multiprotein complexes (Hahm et al., 2004). The formation of the assembly of multi-protein complexes defines why the LIM-containing proteins are involved in diverse biological processes such as cell lineage differentiation and organ development. Dysfunctions of LIM domains induce pathological effects such as embryonic lethality and oncogenesis. LIM domain proteins are the members of a small family of nuclear transcriptional regulators that are important for both normal development and disease processes, and untimely overexpression of this protein may lead to T-cell leukemias (Deane et al; 2003). As a transcription regulator, LMO4 plays a role in transcriptional regulation by forming complexes with selective molecules. LMO4 can also regulate normal and cancer cells' fates via various mechanisms by impairing the cell cycle or apoptosis process or orchestrating cell differentiation (Jane et al., 2001; Tse et al., 2002). LMO4 is induced under hypoxia and protects neurons from ischemic damage (Gomez-Smith et al., 2010). The spatial expression of LMO4 during development also proposes a role for this gene in a number of brain functions, such as autonomic, motor, and neuroendocrine regulation (Hermanson et al., 1999). Much less is known about the role of LMO4 protein in the immune system. However, there are some promising studies. For instance, the analysis of the human protein-protein interaction network allows us to propose that LMO4 and its interaction partner Signal Transducers and Activators of Transcription 3 (STAT3) may become the promising target candidates for immunotherapy of pituitary adenomas (Yang et al.,

2019). Also, functional proteomics mapping suggests that LMO4 interacts with SMAD and BMP pathways (Colland et al., 2004.). The Smad proteins are intracellular effectors of transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β) which regulate cell function, and have strategic roles in development and carcinogenesis (Derynck et al., 2003). BMPs (bone morphogenetic proteins) also participate in cell proliferation, differentiation, and migration (Derynck and Zhang, 2003). The participation of LMO4 protein in different cellular processes was summarized in Figure 1.

Fascinatingly, transcripts encoding LMO4 protein can be detected at great levels in the thymus (Grutz et al., 1998; Kenny et al., 1998; Sugihara et al., 1998) which is a crucial lymphoid organ of the immune system. Overall, the study of LMO4 protein is essential since it plays a vital role in various biological processes and has been implicated in several immune and cancer diseases. Despite some amount of published data in the last two decades, the molecular mechanism of LMO4 regulation in immune systems is still far away from complete understanding. In this literature examination, we emphasize the up-to-date understanding of the role of LMO4 in the immune system through analysis of LMO4 expression in the different immune cells and try to describe what is generally agreed between scientists and what is still under debate.

THE IMMUNE SYSTEM

The immune system is an interactive network of lymphoid organs, cells, humoral factors, and cytokines. The various cells and proteins responsible for immunity constitute the immune system, and their regulation response to defend foreign/non-self-substances (antigen) is known as the immune response.

Figure 1. A schematic overview of LMO4 in different cellular processes. Multiple processes from different features are regulated by LMO4 which determines cell fate.

Two types of immune systems - innate and adaptive together orchestrate and prevent organisms from self and non-self antigens. The innate immunity is the primary and immediate cellular response of the organisms to antigens through the recognition of conserved features of the pathogens. Innate immune system consists of primarily monocytes, macrophages, granulocytes, basophils, neutrophils, natural killer (NK) cells, and dendritic cells (DCs). This first response often results in initial responses from adaptive immunity. Adaptive immunity is modulated through B lymphocytes (humoral) and T lymphocytes (cell-mediated) (Kaper et al; 2004).

LMO4 PROTEIN in IMMUNE CELLS

LMO4 is detected in all types of immune cells and it is expressed widely in basophils and progenitors of immune cells, however, its function in basophils remains indefinable (<https://www.proteinatlas.org/ENSG00000143013-LMO4/immune+cell>). During cell lineage formation, LMO4 is expressed in granulocyte progenitors and is enhanced in the basophil clusters (C12 and C13), demonstrating that it is one of the major drivers of this lineage as a transcription regulator (Paul et al., 2015). Both human and mouse hematopoietic progenitors express LMO4 (Fidanza et al., 2019).

LMO4 ordnates the modulation of the interleukin-6 receptor which is one of the key molecules in immune response and inflammation. Moreover, overexpression of LMO4 induces transcriptional activity and target gene expression of Signal Transducers and Activators of Transcription (Stat 3). STAT3 is one of the most important molecules for the immune system and thanks to the relationship between r LMO4 and STAT3, LMO4 can be considered and needs more investigation in immune cells (Novotny-Diermayr et al., 2005). The schematic view of LMO4 participation in immune cell types is shown in Figure 2.

LMO4 PROTEIN IN INNATE IMMUNITY

Innate immune systems consist of different cells, such as dendritic cells, natural killers, macrophages, mast cells, neutrophils, basophils, and eosinophils which produce cytokines or interact with other cells directly in order to activate the adaptive immune system. Expression of LMO4 in neutrophil cells is observed. During chronic Myeloproliferative Disorders (MPD) expression of LMO4 is increased in neutrophils (Slezak et al., 2009). The level of LMO4, doubled in resolving 4-PBA (Sodium 4-phenylbutyrate, demonstrates the

immunomodulatory effect by restoring neutrophil peroxisome homeostasis and relieving chronic inflammation) trained neutrophils, by binding peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs). Resolving neutrophils in 4-PBA are more mature and have enhanced anti-microbial function as compared to control neutrophils. PPAR γ /LMO4/STAT3 signaling cascade regulates the generation of resolving neutrophils. The level of LMO4 and PPAR γ activation is more than twice the resolving neutrophils (Lin et al., 2022).

Mast cells (MC) are also the main parts of the innate immune system and are evolutionarily old cells and the principal effectors in allergic responses and inflammation. LMO4 is expressed in almost all types of mast cells, such as tongue, dermal, peritoneal, and esophageal mast cells (Krystel-Whittemore et al., 2015). Its mRNA is also abundant in human mast cells (HMC-1), which is a highly immature, malignantly transformed MC line subset. Furthermore, LMO4 regulates neuronal activity through calcium signaling that Ca $_2^+$ is necessary in MC transcriptional programs, this factor may play important roles in the MC lineage as a regulator of the Ca $_2^+$ machinery and beyond. In addition, the obligatory partner of LMO for binding to DNA is LIM domain-binding protein (LDB1) which is highly expressed by MCs (Babina et al., 2022).

LMO4 is a key molecule for Innate lymphoid cells (ILCs) lineage differentiation and their effector functions that play critical roles in defending against infections and maintaining mucosal homeostasis. Yeats4-Lmo4 complex is required for ILC lineage differentiation from common lymphoid progenitors (CLPs) (Liu et al., 2019). Although ILCs are considered innate immune cells, they are also innate counterparts of T cells and are able to secrete cytokines that make a response to pathogenic tissue damage and form adaptive immunity. Despite lacking antigen-specific receptors, ILCs detect changes in the microenvironment through receptors that damaged tissues release (Mjosberg et al., 2016; Ebbo et al., 2017; Bando et al., 2016).

Moreover, LMO4 is activated by PI3K-Akt-mTOR signaling in gastritis cancer and promotes tumor invasiveness and proliferation (Wang et al; 2008). The phosphatidylinositol-3 kinases (PI3Ks) and the mammalian target of the rapamycin (mTOR) pathway have long been known as critically regulating metabolism, growth, or survival. Recent data indicate that these molecules are also key role players in coordinating the innate immune system, thus PI3K and mTOR positively regulate immune cell activation in neutrophils and mast cells. In plasmacytoid dendritic cells, these pathways have recently emerged as important

regulators for type I interferon production via activation of the interferon-regulatory factor. Interestingly, in myeloid immune cells, PI3K and mTOR seem to constrain full immune cell activation by upregulation of the key anti-inflammatory cytokine interleukin 10 and inhibition of proinflammatory cytokines (Weichhart et al; 2008). Silence of LMO4 inhibits PI3K, Akt, and mTOR phosphorylation (Wang et al; 2008). LMO4 expression increases in non-small-cell lung cancer cells and is associated with cell migration and invasion by activating the PI3K/Akt pathway (Wang et al., 2016).

The investigation of the role of LMO4 protein in macrophages and natural killer cells needs to pay more attention because LMO4 is important for macrophage and natural killer cell activation (David et al., 2023). LMO4 is one of the genes that are functional and change their expression during M1 macrophage polarization (Alexander et al., 2020). Furthermore, LMO4 has also been shown to be important in epithelial proliferation, which is an additional component of the innate immune system, since it is a crucial cofactor of the Snail2 gene, which is one of the key regulators of epidermal-mesenchymal transfer (EMT) in neuroblastoma, that provides differentiation and proliferation during the formation of neuronal crests. Snail2 and LMO4 combination repress E-cadherins expression and provide EMT in neuroblastoma and neural crest cells (Feronha et al., 2013). Tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs) are one of the primary infiltrating immune cells in the tumor microenvironment, and they play an indispensable role in the EMT process of tumor cells by interacting with tumor cells (Li et al., 2022).

To summarize, it is clear that the LMO4

protein acts as the transcriptional activator and repressor. We consider that a comprehensive investigation of LMO4, especially its interaction with key role players for the immune system, will provide novel approaches and improve the contribution of the immune system role in preventing cancer, neurodegenerative diseases, and autoimmune disorders.

LMO4 PROTEIN in ADAPTIVE IMMUNITY

T cells are an essential part of the adaptive immune system and are identified in three main groups - cytotoxic (CD8+), helper (CD4+), and regulator (generally CD4+, FOXP3+). LMO4 is functional in T cells, along with its partner LDB1, and is involved in the differentiation of immature T cells, and its aberrant expression impairs this process. Contrary to LMO2, LMO4 is also expressed in mature CD4+/CD8+, CD4+/CD8- and CD4-/CD8+ thymus cells (Kenny et al., 1998; Grutz et al., 1998).

It has been previously shown that LMO2 protein is only found in T cells of lymph nodes and overexpressing of LMO2 causes acute T lymphocytic leukemia (T-ALL). LMO4 associates with LDB1, expressed abundantly in T cells and its abnormal proliferation leads to T-ALL (Grutz et al., 1998; Sum et al., 2005). Consequently, most probably LMO4 also plays a role in T cells. LMO4 expression in Cytokine Induced Killer (CIK) T cells is more than normal T cells (about 1.83-fold). CIK are CD3+ CD56+ T cells with natural killer (NK). Like cytotoxic activity, they show anti-tumor activity and have little or negligible cytotoxicity against normal tissues, so they are used for the immunotherapy of tumors (Franceschetti et al., 2009).

Figure 2. The schematic view of LMO4 PROTEIN participation in immune cell types. LMO4 expresses various cells that have different natures and is functional in most of them.

LMO4 is also expressed in all FOXP3^{+/+} type T cells. FOXP3⁺ T cells are generally regulatory T

cells that prevent auto-immunity and are the main role player in the immune escape of tumors (Chen et al., 2015).

There are differences in the amount of LMO4 in the B cells of individuals between the pediatric and adult forms of Diffuse Large B Cell Lymphoma (DLBCL). At the same time, the amount of LMO4 in both groups is different from that of healthy individuals (Deffenbacher et al., 2012).

Overall, despite exploring the effect of LMO4 on T lymphocyte differentiation and T-ALL with several experimental research, its role in regulator T cells remains completely elusive. Investigation of LMO4 in B cells is the basic level and requires most experimental data.

IMMUNE ESCAPE AND LMO4

According to novel analyses, LMO4 belongs to a new set of genes that can be targeted by immunotherapy in the treatment of adenomas and is considered functional for immune system development and immune system process, tumor cells may be prevented from escaping from the immune system. The dysregulation of LMO4 induced STAT3 activation in the brain and regulated the expression of programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1). Blocking LMO4/STAT3/PD-L1 signaling by recovering the recognition and elimination of cancer cells via CD8⁺ lymphocytes can prevent tumor immune escape (Yang et al., 2019).

CONCLUSION

Taken together, this work can contribute to our understanding of immune cell development, function, and immune-related diseases and the role of LMO4 protein in the immune system and induction of cancer cells. Because the LMO4 protein acts as an activator and repressor, we conclude that regulating cellular processes by obtaining gain-of-function and loss-of-function mutants of LMO4 should be done in the spatial and temporal manner. This knowledge has the prospective to assist the development of novel therapeutic approaches and interventions for immune system disorders and cancer diseases. Generally, by understanding the role of LMO4 in immune cell activation, proliferation, and effector functions, researchers can gain insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying immune responses and immune-related diseases.

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Transkripsiya tənzimləyicisi yalnız-LIM-domain-4 (LMO4) zülalı: İnsan immun sistemindəki rolu

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Orqanizm fərqli hüceyrə siqnalına müxtəlif molekulyar mexanizmlər ilə cavab verir. Bu cür bioloji proseslərdən biri də transkripsiya vasitəsilə tənzimlənmədir. Transkripsiyanın tənzimlənməsi hüceyrənin inkişaf zamanı onun fəaliyyəti və eyniliyini əlaqələndirir. LIM-domeninə malik transkripsiya tənzimləyicisi zülalları müxtəlif hüceyrə prosesləri üçün vacib olan protein ailəsidir. Bu zülallar bir çox əsas hüceyrəvi proseslərini idarə edirlər, o cümlədən xərçəngin - T hüceyrə leykemiyları, süd vəzisi xərçəngi, mədə xərçəngi, neyroblastoma və s. daxil olmaqla, başlanğıcında və ya irəliləməsində iştirak edirlər. LIM domeninin zülal-zülal qarşılıqlı əlaqə qurma qabiliyyətinə görə, LMO4 zülalı yeni transkripsiya komplekslərinin formalaşmasında iştirak edir və gen ekspressiyası proqramlarını tənzimləyə bilər. Bundan əlavə, LMO4 immun sisteminin proqramlaşdırılması və sinir sistemi hüceyrələrinin tənzimlənməsinin vacib hissəsi hesab olunur. Cari tədqiqat işləri xərçəng, neyrodegenerativ xəstəlik və immun sistemi pozğunluqlarında LMO4-ün hədəflənməsinin terapevtik rolunu vurğulayır. Bu araşdırmada LMO4 zülalının immun sistem hüceyrələrində roluna yönəlmiş tədqiqatları ümumiləşdirdik. Çünki, immun hüceyrələri bütün bioloji proseslərin əsas komponentidir, onlar şiş hüceyrələrinin immun qaçışının başladılmasını və dayandırılmasını həyata keçirirlər. LMO4 zülalı hüceyrə proseslərini aktivləşdirmək və ya inhibə etmək üçün məkən və zamanla fəaliyyət göstərdiyindən belə nəticəyə gəlirik ki, bu prosesləri tənzimləmək üçün istifadə etdikləri hüceyrələrdən əvvəl olaraq LMO4 zülalının funksiya-qazanma və funksiya-itirmə qabiliyyətlərinə malik mutantlarını əldə etmək lazımdır. Ümumiyyətlə, LMO4 zülalının insan immun sistemindəki rolunu analiz etməklə, immun cavab reaksiyalarının və immun sistemi ilə bağlı xəstəliklərə cavabdeh olan molekulyar mexanizmlər haqqında məlumat əldə edə biləcəyik.

Açar sözlər: Qazanılmış immun sistemi, immun hüceyrələri, anadangəlmə immun sistemi, insan, LIM-domain zülalları, LMO4, transkripsiya tənzimləyicisi